

METHODS FOR CORRECTING PRE-START CONDITIONS OF YOUNG KURASH WRESTLERS

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Annotation: Elite sports are characterized by high stress, both physical and psycho-emotional. Regulation of pre-start states at the initial stage of training of young kurash wrestlers will make it possible to more effectively build the educational and training process and the process of preparing for competitions.

Key words: young kurash wrestlers, pre-start states, combat readiness, audiovisual stimulation.

Introduction. There is a high level of competition in the competitive activities of kurash wrestlers. A constant increase in the volume and intensity of training loads will not allow achieving the highest achievements in sports, therefore, the search for reserves for further improving sportsmanship is of particular relevance. Such a reserve can be a comprehensive psychological and pedagogical approach to optimizing the preparation of athletes for competitive activity [1, 2, 5].

Managing the training of athletes requires taking into account not only competitive experiences and states, but also those that precede competitions and follow successes or failures in kurash wrestling [3, 4]. The practice of psychological training of athletes convincingly shows that many successes and defeats can be explained in terms of the necessary influence of coaches and athletes themselves on emotional states before the start [6, 7, 8]. It is hardly possible to discount the peculiarities of the mental states of athletes and teams after competitions, because the athlete's psyche is deeply influenced by assessments of the work done.

In the process of preparing for competitions, non-adaptive athletes, which include kurash wrestlers aged 14-15 years, experience a wide range of negative mental states and experiences, the main content of which shows the athlete that he cannot cope with the amount of work required of him and is not approaching the “desired state” their world [9, 12, 14]. In this situation, all the activity of the wrestler should be aimed at scanning stimuli that “threaten” the state of comfort, an intensive search for means and methods of individual adaptation, which is not possible if the athlete does not have special knowledge [10, 11, 13].

In this regard, much attention of researchers is attracted to the methodology of eliminating unwanted emotional experiences by conveying special knowledge to the kurash wrestler in the process of psychological training. To select methods to solve psychological problems in the process of preparing for competitions, many authors study the dynamics of the psychological state of athletes.

Long-term observations of the dynamics of the mental state show that there is a certain shift in the frequency of hyperreactions and hyporeactions under the influence of external and internal conditions of activity, which gradually becomes an individual characteristic of an athlete who has a certain age, social and psychological status [5]. It is precisely based on these individual characteristics that it is necessary to organize the emotional training of a young kurash wrestler.

Emotional preparation is to relieve asthenic, pre-start emotions. An untrained brain during a stressful situation is forced to frantically process information, which entails the production of acetylcholine in meditators and the inability to react to incoming information for a certain time. A well-trained brain does not spend much energy processing information. It follows pre-established paths instead of frantically searching for the right paths [7].

Emotional preparation begins from the moment of preparation for the first competition and is mainly of an individual nature. It is possible to use group psychotherapy to instill collective self-confidence or to relieve tension and fatigue. The following types of pre-launch states are distinguished:

Starting fever, characterized by strong excitement, partial disorganization of behavior, causeless animation, rapid changes in emotional states, instability, errors caused by weakening of memory processes (memorization, recognition, preservation, reproduction, forgetting). Most often, this condition is observed in individuals with a predominance of excitatory processes over inhibitory ones in the nervous system. As a rule, starting fever is accompanied by a decrease in the controlling functions of the cerebral cortex above the subcortex. There is an increase in heart rate and breathing, respiratory surface, excessive sweating, decreased temperature of the extremities, increased tremors, increased frequency of urination. All this leads to the fact that the athlete is not able to use the developed capabilities, makes mistakes even in well-mastered actions, and behaves impulsively and inconsistently.

Starting apathy is caused by the course of nervous processes opposite to those that cause starting fever: inhibitory processes in the nervous system are intensified most often under the influence of severe fatigue or overtraining. There is some drowsiness, sluggishness of movements, general activity and desire to compete decrease, perception and attention are dulled. However, for a number of athletes, after some time (an hour or two), gradually, as the start time approaches, the state of apathy turns into an optimal competitive state. This phenomenon is most often caused by the presence of some undesirable (or unknown) moments in the upcoming competition. Starting apathy has a special type - complacency, which occurs in cases where an athlete is confident in advance of his victory and has a low regard for the capabilities of his opponents. The danger of this condition lies in decreased attention and inability to mobilize in the event of unexpected changes in the situation.

Combat readiness is associated with the optimal ratio of the dynamics of excitatory and inhibitory processes in the nervous system, their balance and optimal mobility. Signs of this state are: focus on the upcoming competition, increased sensitivity and ability to think, effectiveness and sthenic nature of emotions, optimal level of anxiety. In martial arts, combat readiness is characterized by a special clarity of

consciousness, risk-taking, relaxation of muscles and movements, and boundless faith in the possibility of victory [15].

The best ways of emotional preparation, according to researchers, are [4]:

- holding demonstration performances;
- gradual complication of competitive tasks;
- visiting other physical education groups and holding fights there;
- holding non-prestigious fights with more qualified athletes;
- participation in training camps together with representatives of other physical education groups;
- greater participation in away competitions without tasks for results;
- participation in team competitions.

These methods give the most effective results in relieving the emotional experiences of 14-15 year old kurash wrestlers before competitions, which, according to the results of the study, made it possible to increase the quality of performances at competitions.

Conclusions. To summarize, we can say that the mental state of a kurash wrestler, and in particular his emotional background, is an integral part of successful performance in competitions. Psychological training conducted by trainers helps to cope with emotional experiences. To compile psychological training, it is necessary to individually study the influence of external and internal factors on the emotions of a kurash wrestler, therefore individual training is mainly carried out. But this does not negate group psychotherapy to instill collective confidence. We believe that these psychological influences have a positive effect on the performance of kurash wrestlers at competitions.

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